

ADVANTAGES OF THE INTERNATIONAL RULER PROGRAM FOR SOCIAL-EMOTIONAL LEARNING IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN SPECIALIZED SCHOOLS OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article examines the integration of the RULER (SEL) social and emotional learning program into the teaching of English to primary school students in specialized schools in Uzbekistan. The RULER program developed by the Yale Center for Emotional Intelligence in this study highlights the importance of SEL for achieving academic success and developing interpersonal skills in various cultural contexts, as well as improving both socio-emotional competencies and English language proficiency among elementary school students.*

Key words: *RULER program, Social-emotional learning (SEL), English language instruction, Uzbekistan, Emotional literacy, Teacher training, Cultural adaptation, Academic success, Interpersonal skills, Language proficiency.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada RULER (SEL) ijtimoiy va emotsional ta'lim dasturining O'zbekistondagi ixtisoslashtirilgan maktablarda boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilariga ingliz tilini o'qitishga qo'llanishi ko'rib chiqiladi. Ushbu tadqiqotda Yel hissiy intellekt markazi tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan RULER dasturi SELning akademik muvaffaqiyatga erishish va turli madaniy sharoitlarda shaxslararo ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish, shuningdek, boshlang'ich maktab o'quvchilari o'rtasida ijtimoiy-emotsional kompetentsiyalarni va ingliz tilini bilish qobiliyatini yaxshilash uchun muhimligini izlanilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *RULER dasturi, ijtimoiy-emotsional ta'lim (SEL), ingliz tilini o'qitish, O'zbekiston, hissiy savodxonlik, o'qituvchilar malakasini oshirish, madaniy moslashuv, akademik muvaffaqiyat, shaxslararo munosabatlar, tilni bilish.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматривается интеграция программы социально-эмоционального обучения RULER (SEL) в преподавание английского языка ученикам начальных классов специализированных школах Узбекистана. Разработанная Йельским центром эмоционального интеллекта программа RULER в данной исследовании подчеркивается важность SEL для достижения академических успехов и развития навыков межличностного общения в различных культурных контекстах, а так же улучшить как социально-эмоциональные компетенции, так и уровень владения английским языком среди учащихся начальных классов.*

Ключевые слова: *Программа RULER, Социально-эмоциональное обучение (SEL), обучение английскому языку, Узбекистан, Эмоциональная грамотность, Подготовка учителей, Культурная адаптация, Успехи в учебе, Навыки межличностного общения, владение языком.*

Introduction. Choosing a socio-emotional methodology for primary school specialized schools in Uzbekistan with the teaching of English is a multifaceted task that requires consideration of cultural characteristics, linguistic context and the specifics of the educational

process. In modern education, special attention is paid to the importance of social-emotional learning (SEL). This learning encompasses the development of skills necessary for understanding and managing one's emotions, establishing positive relationships, and making responsible decisions. The RULER program, developed by the Yale Center for Emotional Intelligence, offers effective methods for implementing SEL in educational practices. This article focuses on analyzing the advantages of integrating the RULER methodology into English language instruction for primary school students in specialized schools in Uzbekistan.

History of the RULER Program

The first version of the RULER program was developed in 2000 and has since been continuously refined based on new research and practical observations. The main goal of the RULER program is to help students develop emotional literacy and successfully apply these skills in various aspects of their lives (Brackett., 2019).

Core Components of the Program.

- The program includes five components:
 1. Recognizing
 2. Understanding
 3. Labeling
 4. Expressing
 5. Regulating

Each of these components is aimed at fostering necessary skills for successful social adaptation and interaction.

Importance of Social-Emotional Education

Social-emotional education has numerous positive effects, including improved academic performance, reduced levels of stress and conflict among students, as well as the development of cooperation and communication skills (Durlak et al., 2011). Such skills become particularly important in the context of Uzbekistan's multilingual and multicultural society, where an increasing number of students from various cultural and linguistic backgrounds presents unique challenges for the educational system.

RULER Program and Its Benefits for Uzbekistan.

One of the most effective and practical international methods for social and emotional education that can be implemented in teaching English to primary school students in specialized schools in Uzbekistan is SEL (Social and Emotional Learning), namely the RULER program. Implementing the RULER program in Uzbekistan's educational practices can lead to significant changes in teaching. It is consider the main advantages of applying this methodology.

- Integration of Emotional Literacy into the Educational Process

Embedding emotional literacy principles into English language lessons enhances students' understanding of the material. The RULER program provides various methodologies that help students connect language with emotions, increasing motivation and interest in language learning.

- Development of Language Skills through Social-Emotional Learning

The RULER methodology can be integrated into language instruction through practical assignments such as role-playing, discussions, and text analyses. Students can engage with materials that reflect emotional situations, thereby developing not only language skills but also abilities in empathy and cooperation (Mamatkulov, S. (2020).

- Support in the Context of Sociocultural Changes

Uzbekistan is implementing reforms in education aimed at modernizing schools and improving the quality of education. The RULER program can assist in addressing the challenges associated with changes in curricula and teaching methods. The application of SEL can foster a more positive classroom environment and contribute to more productive educational processes.

Implementing the RULER Program in Specialized Schools of Uzbekistan

- Teacher Preparation

Implementing the program requires enhancing teachers' skills and training. Educators must be educated in the fundamentals of social-emotional learning and methods for applying RULER in the classroom. This may include seminars, workshops, and online courses.

- Adaptation to Local Conditions

The RULER program should be adapted to the cultural and social conditions of Uzbekistan. Basic concepts of the program can be supplemented with local examples and contexts to make the education more relevant to students.

- Evaluating Effectiveness

To assess the effectiveness of the program implementation, regular research and surveys among students and teachers need to be conducted. This will allow for the identification of positive changes and the adjustment of approaches if necessary (Elias., 1997).

Conclusion

The implementation of the RULER program for social-emotional education in English language teaching in specialized schools of Uzbekistan can lead to sustainable changes in educational approaches. The development of emotional literacy not only improves students' language skills but also fosters a positive and supportive educational environment. It is crucial that the realization of this program is conducted with consideration of local conditions and the needs of both educators and students.

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